

Morphology-Dependent Properties of Magnetite Nanoparticles for MRI and Biomedical Use

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Magnetic nanoparticles have emerged as promising tools in biomedicine due to their unique physicochemical properties and multifunctionality. In this study, the synthesis and characterization of magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles with controlled geometries – hexagonal prisms, concave cubes, and nanoplates are presented, with the aim of evaluating the influence of shape on their properties and biomedical potential. The nanoparticles were synthesized via thermal decomposition of organometallic precursors. Structural and morphological analyses confirmed the formation of monodisperse nanostructures with a pure magnetite phase. Magnetic measurements revealed shape-dependent variations in coercivity and magnetization behavior. Cytotoxicity studies using LNCaP and PC-3 cell lines demonstrated low toxicity across all nanoparticle types, confirming their biocompatibility. The performance of the nanoparticles as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents was assessed through T₂ relaxivity measurements, which showed that anisotropic particles, particularly nanoplates, exhibit significantly enhanced contrast efficiency (up to 280 mM⁻¹·s⁻¹) compared to previously reported spherical counterparts (170-208 mM⁻¹·s⁻¹). These findings highlight the critical role of nanoparticle geometry in determining functional properties and demonstrate that shape-engineered magnetite nanoparticles are promising candidates for advanced biomedical applications, including MRI diagnostics and targeted drug delivery.

1. Introduction

The application of nanomaterials in medicine and pharmacology represents a priority research direction, enabling the resolution of some of the most pressing challenges in these fields. Highlighting magnetic nanoparticles among nanoscale structures, they frequently emerge as promising biomedical tools. Magnetic nanoparticles, which are comparable in size to biological entities such as cells, can act as multifunctional agents for combined therapy (hyperthermia, targeted drug delivery) [1, 2, 16] and diagnostics (magnetic resonance imaging) [6], as well as serve as components of composite biomedical materials [10]. The unique properties of magnetic nanoparticles determine their broad range of applications in biomedicine and other fields. For successful application in medicine, particles must meet several fundamental requirements: they must be sufficiently small in size, biocompatible, and it must be possible to

influence them in some manner within a living organism. Certain applications also require the ability to further surface functionalize the particles, among other criteria.

Iron oxide nanoparticles satisfy these requirements and therefore find widespread application in various biomedical tasks. Their size can be tuned during synthesis from a few to hundreds of nanometers [7, 17], which is smaller than the size of cells (10–100 μm) and comparable to the dimensions of viruses (20–450 nm), proteins (5–50 nm), or genes (2 nm in width and 10–100 nm in length). Owing to their small size, they can selectively interact with and penetrate target biological entities. In addition, their surface can be modified with biologically active molecules capable of selective interaction with target biological structures, thereby enabling controlled, site-specific effects at the nanoscale.

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Iron oxide nanoparticles exhibit magnetic properties, which means that they can be controlled using an external magnetic field gradient [8]. This remote controllability, combined with the intrinsic permeability of biological tissues to magnetic fields, opens up significant prospects for the manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles within living organisms. In particular, the application of a magnetic field enables the targeted delivery of anticancer drugs to tumor sites. [12] In addition to the aforementioned properties, magnetic nanoparticles also exhibit an effect known as hyperthermia [13, 21], i.e., the ability of nanoparticles to heat up due to the resonant conversion of energy from an alternating magnetic field into heat.

One of the most important applications of magnetic nanoparticles is magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [6]. The presence of nanoparticles in an organ or tissue can significantly enhance the MR signal. The use of magnetic targeting and conjugation with marker molecules enables the accumulation of particles in a specific organ. A key aspect for MRI is the attachment of nanoparticles to the cell surface followed by their internalization (endocytosis). Such nanoparticles are selectively taken up by the cells lining blood vessels, whose function is to remove foreign substances from the bloodstream; therefore, MRI contrast depends on the differential uptake by various tissues. A size-dependent effect is also observed: nanoparticles with diameters of 30 nm or larger rapidly accumulate in the liver and spleen, whereas particles with sizes of 10 nm or smaller remain in circulation for longer periods [15].

The use of contrast agents based on magnetic nanoparticles significantly improves the spatial resolution of MRI. Nonspherical nanostructures are considered more efficient T2 contrast agents due to their larger surface area compared to spherical particles of the same volume [23]. The relaxivity value is also proportional to the saturation magnetization (M_s) of magnetic contrast agents [4, 5].

According to literature data, the shape of nanoparticles can significantly influence both their physicochemical properties and their biological activity [19], as well as their in vivo dynamics [3]. There are a number of studies that have investigated the effect of nanoparticle shape on the efficiency of their biomedical applications, [9, 11, 20] including their use as MRI agents. However, in this work, we consider alternative geometries that demonstrate higher efficiency compared to conventional spherical particles. In particular, this study considers Fe_3O_4 nanoplates as well as hexagonal nanoprisms and concave cubes, which may be effectively applied in biomedicine, including MRI diagnostics.

2. Results and Discussion

In this work, iron oxide nanoparticles of various sizes and shapes were synthesized using the thermal decomposition of organometallic precursors in high-boiling organic solvents. This method enables the production of monodisperse particles with high crystallinity over a wide size range. During the initiation of the chemical reaction, control over nucleation and growth processes was achieved by varying the heating rate of the reaction mixture, the synthesis time, and the ratios of the system components.

By adjusting different synthesis conditions, powders of nanoparticles with diverse sizes and morphologies were obtained. Their characterization was carried out using transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Figure 1 presents TEM images along with the corresponding size distributions for different types of synthesized nanoparticles (hexagonal nanoprisms, concave cubes, and nanoplates).

Figure 1. TEM images of nanoparticles with different morphologies (insets: calculated particle size distributions): (a) hexagonal prisms; (b) concave cubes; (c) nanoplates.

Table 1. XRD and TEM measurement results for nanoparticles of various shapes.

Sample	Crystallite size (nm)	TEM size (nm)	Phase composition	Lattice parameters (nm)
Hexagonal prisms	47 ± 5	55 ± 3	100 % Fe ₃ O ₄	0,8395 ± 0.0004
Concave cubes	24 ± 2	19.0 ± 1.7	100 % Fe ₃ O ₄	0,8386 ± 0.0004
Nanoplates	5 ± 1	12.0 ± 0.6	100 % Fe ₃ O ₄	0,8372 ± 0.0004

To determine the phase composition and crystal structure of the studied nanoparticles, X-ray diffraction analysis was performed using the powder diffraction method. The lattice parameters and crystallite sizes were evaluated. Figure 2 shows the diffraction patterns of the samples, and the numerical values of the measured parameters are presented in Table 1.

Figure 2. Results of XRD measurements of nanoparticle samples with different morphologies.

A spinel-type structure (H1.1) is characteristic of magnetite (Fe₃O₄) and one of the modifications of iron oxide, maghemite (γ-Fe₂O₃). The lattice parameters of these stoichiometric phases are close in value: a = 0.8397 nm (for Fe₃O₄) and a = 0.835 nm (for γ-Fe₂O₃). Since the measured lattice parameters are closer to the reference values for magnetite, it can be assumed that the phase identified in the diffraction patterns corresponds to magnetite.

Magnetic properties were measured at room temperature using a vibrating sample magnetometer. The results of magnetic measurements of chemically synthesized iron oxide nanopowders are presented in Table 2. The measurement error did not exceed 0.2% for magnetization and 0.5% for coercivity (Figure 3).

To evaluate the stability of the particles in water, ζ-potential measurements were carried out. The obtained nanoparticles exhibit a pronounced nega-

Figure 3. Dependences of magnetization on the applied magnetic field for nanoparticles of various shapes: (a) Hexagonal prisms; (b) concave cubes; (c) nanoplates.

Table 2. Results of magnetic measurements of nanoparticles of various shapes.

Sample	Size, nm	Coercivity H _c , kA/m (Oe)	Kernance 4πI _r , A·m ² /kg	Saturation magnetization 4πI _s , A·m ² /kg
Hexagonal prisms	55	8.3 (104)	12.8	88.3
Concaved cubes	19	3.6 (45)	5.7	87.4
Nanoplates	12	4.8 (60)	2.1	52.1

tive ζ-potential, indicating a low tendency toward aggregation. According to classical colloid chemistry concepts, hydrosols are considered stable when the absolute value of the ζ-potential exceeds 30 mV. The sample in the form of concave cubes shows a lower value of this parameter (24.4 mV); however, these colloids are additionally stabilized by steric hindrance provided by the surrounding polymer shell of Pluronic F127, which prevents coagulation.

Following synthesis in an organic medium, a modification step was performed, involving the phase transfer of nanoparticles from the organic phase into water. This was achieved by magnetic stirring of a toluene solution containing the nanoparticles with an aqueous solution of Pluronic F127 (C = 2 mmol/L) for 24 hours.

Thus, with potential further functionalization, the obtained magnetite nanoparticles may be used for biomedical applications as agents for targeted drug delivery and as contrast agents for MRI.

For medical applications, one of the most critical characteristics is the biocompatibility of nanoparticles. Therefore, cytotoxicity studies of the samples were conducted using human malignant tumor cell cultures, specifically LNCaP and PC3. The results are presented as histograms of cell viability after 48 hours of incubation with magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) of different shapes (Figure 4).

Upon incubation of cells with hexagonal prism-shaped nanoparticles, the PC-3 cell line was found to be more sensitive. The minimum cell viability for PC-3 was 83.2% at a nanoparticle concentration of 7.1 μg/mL, whereas for LNCaP it was 97.2% at 50 μg/mL.

For concave cube-shaped nanoparticles, the minimum viability for PC-3 cells was 90.3% at a concentration of 7.1 μg/mL, while for LNCaP cells it was 91.5% at 5 μg/mL.

In the case of nanoplates, the PC-3 culture again exhibited higher sensitivity: the minimum viability for PC-3 was 90.3% at a concentration of 7.1 μg/mL, while for LNCaP it was 92% at 12.5 μg/mL.

Finally, the potential application of the synthesized nanoparticles for MRI was investigated. A key parameter of MRI contrast agents is the T₂ relaxivity, which characterizes how efficiently a contrast agent enhances the decay of the MRI signal

Figure 4. Results of cytotoxicity studies of nanoparticles with different morphologies on LNCaP (green) and PC-3 (blue) cell lines: (a) hexagonal prisms; (b) concaved cubes; (c) nanoplates.

associated with T₂ relaxation. It is typically expressed as the increase in the relaxation rate (1/T₂) per unit concentration of the substance. The measured dependences of 1/T₂ on concentration, along with the results of their linear fitting, are presented in Figure 5. The results showed that iron oxide nanoplates exhibit the highest relaxivity (280 mM⁻¹·s⁻¹), while the relaxivity value of concave cubes is slightly lower (262 mM⁻¹·s⁻¹). However, both values exceed the relaxivity reported earlier for spherical particles (170-208 mM⁻¹·s⁻¹) [11, 14]. Hexagonal prisms demonstrated relatively low contrast efficiency, which is most likely associated

with their low colloidal stability, characteristic of magnetic nanoparticles of such large sizes.

Figure 5. Dependence of the relaxation rate on Fe concentration for nanoparticles of different shapes: (a) hexagonal prisms, (b) concave cubes, (c) nanoplates.

3. Conclusion

In this study, magnetite nanoparticles with controlled shapes – hexagonal prisms, concave cubes, and nanoplates were successfully synthesized via thermal decomposition of organometallic precursors. Comprehensive characterization demonstrated that the physicochemical and magnetic properties of the nanoparticles are strongly dependent on their geometry. In particular, variations in particle shape significantly influenced coercivity, colloidal stability, and magnetic behavior. The nanoparticles exhibited sufficient stability in aqueous media after

surface modification and showed low cytotoxicity toward human prostate cancer cell lines, confirming their biocompatibility and suitability for biomedical applications. Importantly, the MRI studies revealed that anisotropic nanostructures, especially nanoplates and concave cubes, exhibit enhanced T_2 relaxivity compared to conventional spherical nanoparticles. Nanoplates demonstrated the highest contrast efficiency, highlighting the critical role of morphology in optimizing imaging performance.

Overall, the results confirm that tailoring nanoparticle shape is a powerful strategy for tuning their functional properties. The synthesized magnetite nanostructures show strong potential as advanced agents for magnetic resonance imaging and targeted drug delivery, paving the way for further development of shape-engineered nanomaterials in biomedicine.

Method

Reagents

Iron(III) oleate ($\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{33}\text{COO})_3$), iron(III) acetylacetonate ($\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{O}_2)_3$), oleic acid ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$, 90%), stearic acid ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$, 99.8%), sodium oleate ($\text{NaC}_{17}\text{H}_{33}\text{COO}$), 1-octadecene ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}$, 90%), anisole ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}$), hexane (C_6H_{14} , 80%), ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$, 95%), toluene (C_7H_8), deionized water (H_2O).

Synthesis

In this work, magnetite nanoparticles of various shapes and sizes were synthesized via thermal decomposition of organometallic precursors in high-boiling solvents. The magnetite nanoparticle samples were prepared in an organic medium. The sample of nanoparticles in the form of hexagonal prisms was obtained by thermal decomposition of iron(III) acetylacetonate ($\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$) according to the method reported by H. Wang [18]. The reaction mixture consisted of 2 mmol of iron(III) acetylacetonate, 4.5 mmol of oleic acid, 1.75 mmol of stearic acid, and 10 mL of benzyl ether. After dehydration for 1 hour at 120 °C under an argon atmosphere, the reaction mixture was heated to 290 °C at a rate of 40 °C/min. With simultaneous magnetic stirring, the temperature of 290 °C was maintained for 30 minutes. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature, and the nanoparticles were precipitated in hexane and subsequently transferred into toluene. Magnetite nanocubes were synthesized by thermal decomposition of iron(III) oleate according to the approach described in [22]. The reaction mixture (1 mmol of iron(III) oleate,

0.05 mmol of sodium oleate, 0.5 mmol of oleic acid, and 12 mL of benzyl ether) was heated to 120 °C for 20 minutes to remove residual water. Subsequently, under magnetic stirring, the mixture was heated at a rate of 5 °C/min to reflux and maintained at this temperature for 60 minutes.

Nanoplates: The reaction mixture consisted of 5 mmol of iron(III) oleate, 5 mmol of sodium oleate, and 25 mL of 1-octadecene. Degassing and dehydration were carried out at 120 °C for 30 minutes under magnetic stirring in an argon atmosphere, after which the reaction mixture was heated at a rate of 1 °C/min to 210 °C and maintained at this temperature for 15 hours. Finally, the mixture was heated to 240 °C and kept for 1 hour. After cooling to room temperature, the nanoparticles were precipitated using hexane. After synthesis of all samples, the nanoparticles were transferred into a more biocompatible medium by magnetic stirring of the nanoparticle dispersion in toluene with an aqueous solution of Pluronic F127.

Characterization

Particle size distribution and ζ -potential measurements were performed using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS instrument (scattering angle 173°) equipped with a He-Ne laser. The morphology and size of the obtained iron oxide nanoparticles were determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a JEOL JEM-2100 microscope. Phase analysis of the investigated materials for determining crystallographic structure parameters was performed using a DRON-4 X-ray diffractometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out using a Quantum Design Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS) equipped with a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) insert (magnetic field up to 7100 kA/m (90 kOe), temperature range from -271 to 76 °C).

T_2 relaxivity was determined using a ClinScan magnetic resonance imaging system operating at a magnetic field strength of 7 T. MRI images of test tubes containing nanoparticle solutions with known Fe^{3+} concentrations were acquired in Spin-Echo mode with parameters TR = 10000 ms and TE = 8, 16, 24, ..., 240 ms. The signal intensity in each test tube was then evaluated, and the T_2 relaxation time was calculated using the following equation:

$$S_i = S_0 e^{-\frac{TE}{T_2}}$$

where S_0 is the signal at the initial time point and S_i is the signal at time TE. The T_2 relaxivity was determined as the slope of the linear dependence of $1/T_2$ on nanoparticle concentration.

Cytotoxicity studies were performed using human prostate cancer cell lines LNCaP and PC-3. Cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 90,000 cells/mL for LNCaP and 50,000 cells/mL for PC-3. Cell counting was carried out using a hemocytometer (Goryaev chamber). After 24 hours, a solution of magnetic nanoparticles in distilled water was added to the cells. The cells were then incubated with magnetic nanoparticles for 48 hours. MTT reagent (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) at a concentration of 5 mg/mL was added to the cells, resulting in a final concentration of 500 μ g/mL in the culture medium. The cells were incubated with the MTT solution for 35 minutes in a CO₂ incubator. Subsequently, the medium was removed from each well, and 60 μ L of DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) was added. Optical density measurements were recorded using a Multiskan Go spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 570 nm.

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Authors' contributions:

MK: Writing original draft, data collection, visualization. **TN:** Investigation, writing original draft. **MA:** Resources, project administration. **IS:** Methodology, investigation. **AA:** Supervising, project administration. **AS:** Methodology, resources.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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